

ISic0413

I.Sicily inscription 0413

Language

Latin

Type

funerary; building
(?)

Material

marble

Object

architrave

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates**

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 920

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [--- vi]r primario VI,I[---]

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175782

EDR 081525

EDCS 21900476

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae

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1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1989.0342g

Manganaro, G. 1989. Iscrizioni Latine nuove e vecchie della Sicilia. *Epigraphica*. 51: 161-196. At 183 no.64 fig.69

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